

Experimental Validation of an Efficient DRL-based Routing and Spectrum Assignment for Optical Network Automation

Carlos Hernández-Chulde, Ramon Casellas, Ricardo Martínez, Ricard Vilalta and Raul Muñoz

Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC-CERCA), Castelldefels, Barcelona 08860, Spain

e-mail: chernandez@cttc.es

ABSTRACT

This work explores the application of Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) for Routing and Spectrum Assignment (RSA) in Elastic Optical Networks (EONs). By capitalizing on the inherent capabilities of DRL to manage complex and dynamic service demands and network conditions, this demo showcases the seamless integration of a DRL approach with an enhanced Software-Defined Networking (SDN) control plane for enabling more intelligent, flexible, and efficient optical network management. We validate this integration by utilizing CTTC's ADRENALINE testbed®, where a trained DRL agent assisting on the path and resource selection function is effectively interfaced with a full-fledge SDN control plane implementation. This validation confirms both the practical applicability of the DRL approach on supporting selected control functions, and industry-standard interfaces in operational EON infrastructures, while also highlighting the potential for future innovations in optical network automation.

Keywords: Routing and Spectrum Assignment, Elastic Optical Networks, Deep Reinforcement Learning, Software Defined Networking.

1. OVERVIEW

With the advent of B5G and 6G communication technologies, which promise a multitude of connectivity services and verticals, the demands on optical networks have become more diverse and stringent. These demands necessitate greater flexibility, adaptability, and programmability in network operations to accommodate high capacity, low latency, and guaranteed reliability. To address the increasing demands on network services, it is essential to upgrade the existing network architecture and management schemes. This involves not only enhancing the physical infrastructure but also adopting new strategies for network operation. Optical network operators are at the forefront of this transformation, working to optimize capital expenditure (CAPEX), operational expenses (OPEX), and energy consumption. Their goal is to support vast transport capacities and accommodate a growing user/device base with diverse connectivity needs, all while ensuring economic and energy efficiency.

The evolution of optical networks is marked by a shift from traditional fixed-grid Wavelength Division Multiplexing networks, which struggle to meet varying traffic demands due to their inflexible granularity. In response, elastic optical networks (EONs) emerged as a solution. These networks are characterized by their flex-grid design, allowing for the provision of spectrum with variable-sized widths tailored to different traffic demands, thereby enhancing overall spectrum utilization. Characterized by high throughput and transmission flexibility, EONs are gaining significant attention as the most promising architecture for the next-generation backbone network. Additionally, the adoption of software-defined networking (SDN) principles provides network programmability and fast reconfiguration, maximizing the benefits of EONs in network programmability and spectrum management [1]. SDN's role in disaggregating optical networks further enhances programmability and flexibility while reducing vendor lock-in, thus driving innovation in optical network architectures.

The transition of optical networks towards a flexible grid EONs, where the optical spectrum is partitioned into small frequency slot units (FSs), has increased the complexity of network resource management. Routing and Spectrum Assignment (RSA) challenge is a pivotal aspect of EONs, requiring the establishment of end-to-end lightpaths (involving nodes and links) and the allocation of a contiguous set of FSs tailored to the bandwidth demands of diverse traffic requests while optimizing optical spectrum utilization. Traditional approaches to RSA often grapple with the high complexity and dynamic nature of modern network demands, frequently being unable to optimize network resources while meeting strict service requirements.

The application of machine learning (ML) techniques in optical networks is a growing trend to achieve greater intelligence and automation in control and orchestration operations [2]. Recent advancements in ML techniques, particularly deep reinforcement learning (DRL), have shown promise in optimizing resource allocation in optical networks. The application of DRL methodologies to the domain of RSA in EONs offers a compelling solution exploiting the benefits tied to DRL on learning optimal policies through interaction with the environment. By framing RSA as a decision-making problem under dynamic network environments, DRL enables the network to manage spectrum resources adaptively and intelligently, thus optimizing the fulfilment of service requirements (i.e. latency and bandwidth) in real-time.

This work demonstrates and validates on-demand RSA computations derived from (offline) trained DRL agents. By doing so, upon a connectivity service demand, the SDN control function of path and resource selection done in the CTTC's ADRENALINE testbed® is realized using those ML-trained RSA models.

2. INNOVATION

The core innovation of this research resides in the exploitation of trained DRL agent for RSA computation within a ML-assisted SDN control plane, which exemplifies a significant leap towards autonomous network operation. This brings more intelligent, efficient, and flexible network management and control strategies that can dynamically adapt to varying service demands and network conditions.

In Figure 1 (a), it is shown the SDN Control Plane architecture. The *SDN controller* is responsible for the entire service lifecycle comprising: i) the processing of new service requests; ii) finding and allocating the necessary EON resources (e.g., optical spectrum); iii) configuring the involved network elements (e.g., optical switches); and finally, iv) releasing resources once a service is completed. The SDN controller offers an API through the northbound interface (NBI) for operations/business support systems (OSS/BSS) or end-users to request connectivity services. The NBI implementation is based on the ONF T-API 2.1, which is built upon RESTCONF protocol and YANG models. A relevant computational-intensive control function being externalized in a dedicated entity is the path computation and optical resource selection (i.e., RSA). Hence, the SDN controller delegates RSA decisions to the so-called *ML-assisted path computation element* (PCE). This enables flexible and scalable execution of RSA algorithms, as they can be updated and executed in a modular fashion, offloading the controller. The ML-assisted PCE handles the development and deployment of ML models to support RSA decision-making processes. For the exchange of path computation requests and responses, the ML-assisted PCE acts as a server exposing a REST API to the client SDN controller.

In the workflow depicted in Figure 1 (b), the EON infrastructure and connectivity services are managed by a single SDN controller instance. The OSS/BSS/User requests the provisioning of a Digital Signal Rate (DSR) connectivity service, i.e., a lightpath between two Service Interface Points (SIPs) which are mapped to specific add/drop ports on reconfigurable optical add/drop multiplexers (ROADM). A SIP encompasses spectrum availability, in terms of FSs. The service request includes a given spectrum width and/or additional constraints such as maximum tolerated latency. Upon such a request, the SDN controller sends a path computation request to the ML-assisted PCE. In the PCE, the RSA decision process first retrieves an updated *snapshot* of network state from the SDN controller. The network information (i.e., topology, available resources, and active connectivity services) is exchanged in the so-called TAPI context. This context information is used by the PCE to compute the path, i.e., making the RSA decision, using a ML model previously generated with a DRL agent. If the computation succeeds, the PCE communicates the path and spectrum resources back to the SDN controller, including the list of selected links, and FSs. The SDN controller then performs the resource allocation on the underlying network devices involved along the computed path. This entails configuring the specific transponders and ROADMs via Southbound Interfaces (SBIs). Finally, the SDN controller communicates the successful provisioning of a connectivity service to the OSS/BSS/User.

Figure 1. (a) SDN control plane architecture, and (b) Service provisioning workflow.

3. DEMO CONTENT & IMPLEMENTATION

The setup for our demonstration illustrates a cutting-edge approach for RSA in EONs by leveraging a trained DRL agent. This setup involves a real-world emulation of a functional EON infrastructure using the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed[®]. All the architectural components were deployed within Docker containers for streamlined operation of the emulated EON. Figure 2. Illustrative layout of the demo components provides a comprehensive view of the structure and functionality of the demo components.

Central to our demo is the SDN controller, functioning as an Optical Line System (OLS) Controller, with the primary function of managing service connection requests—both provisioning new connections and deleting existing ones. The emulated EON comprises 14 optical nodes (ROADMs) interconnected by 21 bidirectional optical links working in the C-band. As described before, the provisioning of new connectivity services entails the interaction between the SDN controller and the PCE. The SDN controller sends a POST request to the PCE

requesting the path computation. The PCE executes the RSA decisions. To this end, updated network information and service requirements are used as input data into a trained ML model. The network information is obtained by sending a GET request to the SDN controller. The PCE parses the received TAPI context to determine the current network utilization. The input for the ML model consists of i) source and destination nodes; ii) the required number of FSs and the maximum tolerated latency for the request, and iii) the current spectrum utilization of several candidate paths (see Fig. 2). The spectrum utilization encapsulates the position of the first available FS block, the average size of these blocks, and the total number of available FSs, all integral in painting a comprehensive picture of available spectrum resources for the ML model within the PCE, more details are given in [3]. The trained ML model then processes such data to select the most viable path (*action*) from a set of candidate ones, focusing on optimizing network throughput while adhering to the predefined service constraints. Once the path is selected, detailed by a list of links and FSs, and notified to the SDN controller, the latter coordinates the programming of the underlying network devices to complete the service provisioning. It is within the purview of the SDN controller to implement these RSA decisions by orchestrating the network elements to materialize the desired connectivity service.

Figure 2. Illustrative layout of the demo components.

Service connection requests can be generated through two distinct methods; the first employs a Python script aimed to create a series of service connections. Each connection is characterized by a random pair of source and destination SIPs, required bandwidth, and a maximum tolerated latency. These connections arrive and depart dynamically in accordance with a predefined traffic load pattern. The traffic generator, acting as an OSS, initiates new service connections via POST requests and similarly signals the termination of services upon completion. Alternatively, a Graphical User Interface (GUI) provides a more interactive way of requesting service provisioning. Through the GUI running in another container, users can manually input the required parameters such as source and destination SIPs, and bandwidth, for connectivity services, as depicted in Fig 3. The GUI also provides real-time insights into the network's current state, displaying the network topology, active connectivity services, and the spectrum usage across links, enriching the user's understanding of the network's dynamics as illustrated in Figures 4, 5, and 6. This dual-method approach in generating service connections underlines our setup's flexibility, facilitating an immersive demonstration experience.

Note that the inference made by the ML model plays a crucial role in the RSA decision-making. The ML model employed for this purpose was generated through the training of a DRL agent, presented in [3], using the Asynchronous Advantage Actor-Critic (A3C) algorithm. The process of designing the DRL agent involved several tasks, including the definition of the network state representation used as input for the neural networks of the agent. This representation includes essential details like service connection requirements and the current spectrum utilization across multiple candidate paths. The neural network architecture was meticulously designed, specifying the number of layers and neurons in the neural networks. The formulation of the reward function was pivotal in guiding the agent towards desired outcomes. During training, the DRL agent assimilates this information, making informed decisions to select the most appropriate candidate path for servicing new connection requests, which represents the output of the neural networks. More details about the state, action, and reward of the DRL agent are provided in [3]. The paramount objective of this training phase was to refine a ML model to consistently

achieve the maximum cumulative reward, interpreted as the optimum allocation of bandwidth across the network, while also adhering to stringent latency constraints.

Figure 3. GUI – Service creation interface.

Figure 5. GUI – Number of active services.

Figure 4. GUI – Topology view.

Figure 6. GUI – Link spectrum usage.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This demonstration showcases the interactions between the OSS/BSS, SDN controller, PCE, and the ML model, to handle autonomously the provisioning of connectivity service request. The resulting modular control operations and interactions favor the integration of advanced ML models in selected SDN control operations such as the path computation and resource selections (i.e., RSA decisions). Designed as a comprehensive showcase of leveraging DRL for RSA in EONs, this demonstration underscores both the technical prowess and the practical applicability of the approach in meeting the stringent and heterogenous requirements of emerging services and applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has received funding from the EU’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program, SEASON project, grant agreement no. 101096120. It is partially funded by the RELAMPAGO grant PID2021-127916OB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER/UE and by ERDF A way of making Europe, and “Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital” and the European Union-NextGenerationEU in the frameworks of the “Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia” and of the “Mecanismo de Recuperación y Resiliencia” under references TSI-063000-2021-22, TSI-063000-2021-23, TSI-063000-2021-115.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Li, R. Zhang, X. Tian, and Z. Zhu, “Multi-agent and cooperative deep reinforcement learning for scalable network automation in multi-domain SD-EONs,” *IEEE Trans. Netw. Serv. Manage.* 18, 4801–4813 (2021).
- [2] R. Gu, Z. Yang, and Y. Ji, “Machine learning for intelligent optical networks: a comprehensive survey,” *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.* 157, 102576 (2020).
- [3] C. Hernández-Chulde, R. Casellas, R. Martínez, R. Vilalta, and R. Muñoz, “Experimental evaluation of a latency-aware routing and spectrum assignment mechanism based on deep reinforcement learning,” *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 15, 925-937 (2023)